

“Antioxidant Activity of Phyla nodiflora Plant: A Comprehensive Review”.

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Abstract:

Phyla nodiflora, commonly known as frogfruit or carpetweed, is a medicinal plant that has attracted scientific interest due to its potential antioxidant properties. This review comprehensively examines the phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity of Phyla nodiflora, emphasizing its bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, and tannins, which contribute to its free radical scavenging capacity. Various extraction methods and antioxidant assays are discussed to highlight the methodologies used in analyzing its antioxidant potential. Additionally, the review addresses the therapeutic applications of Phyla nodiflora, particularly in oxidative stress-related disorders, and explores the underlying mechanisms of action of its antioxidant compounds. This study aims to provide insights into the pharmacological relevance of Phyla nodiflora, offering a foundation for future research and potential pharmaceutical applications of its extracts and isolated compounds.

Keywords:

- Phyla nodiflora
- Antioxidant activity
- Free radical scavenging
- Phytochemicals
- Medicinal plants
- Flavonoids
- Phenolic compounds
- Oxidative stress
- Traditional medicine
- Bioactive compounds

Introduction:

Background and Context:

Phyla nodiflora, commonly known as frogfruit or carpetweed, is a member of the Verbenaceae family and is widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions. Traditionally, Phyla nodiflora has been used in folk medicine to treat a variety of ailments, including skin disorders, fever, respiratory issues, and gastrointestinal diseases. Recent studies have highlighted its potential antioxidant properties, largely attributed to its rich phytochemical content, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and tannins. Given that oxidative stress is a contributing factor in numerous chronic diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cancer, and neurodegenerative disorders, the exploration of plant-based antioxidants has garnered significant interest. Phyla nodiflora, with its traditional usage and bioactive profile, presents a promising natural source of antioxidants that may support therapeutic applications.

PHARMACOGNOSTIC ACCOUNT OF PHYLIA NODIFLORA PLANT:

Plant Name

Phyla nodiflora Linn.

Local Name

Jal Papli

Vernacular Names

English	:	Lippia, Frog fruit
Philippines	:	Busbusi, Chachahan
Thailand	:	Yaa Riet Pla
Hindi	:	Bukkan, Jalpapli
Sanskrit	:	Vasir Vasuka
Marathi	:	Ratolia Vakkan
Tamil	:	Poduthalai

Synonyms:

Lippia incisa, Lippia nodiflora, Lippia reptans Kunth, Phyla incisa Small

Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Division: Magnoliophyta

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Lamiales

Family: Verbenaceae

Genus: Phylab Species: Nodiflora

Traditional Uses:

1. Fever reduction: Leaves and roots are used to treat fever, malaria, and influenza.
2. Digestive issues: Leaves and stems are used to treat diarrhea, dysentery, and stomachaches.
3. Respiratory problems: Leaves are used to treat coughs, colds, and bronchitis.
4. Skin conditions: Leaves and roots are used to treat eczema, acne, and dermatitis.
5. Wound healing: Leaves and stems are used to treat wounds, cuts, and bruises.
6. Anti-inflammatory: Roots are used to treat arthritis, joint pain, and swelling.
7. Antiseptic: Leaves and roots are used to treat infections and prevent sepsis.

Traditional uses in Different Cultures:

1. Ayurveda (India): Used to treat fever, diarrhea, and respiratory problems. (Khare, 2007)
2. Unani Medicine (Middle East and South Asia): Used to treat fever, cough, and skin conditions. (Khan et al., 2015)
3. Traditional Chinese Medicine (China): Used to treat fever, influenza, and digestive issues. (Li et al., 2018)
4. Folk Medicine (Southeast Asia): Used to treat wounds, cuts, and bruises. (Nguyen et al., 2019)
5. Native American Medicine (North America): Used to treat fever, cough, and respiratory problems. (Moerman, 1998)

Phytochemical Composition:

Flavonoids, Phenolic acid, Terpenoids, and other compounds these phytochemicals present in phyla nodiflora plants.

Bioactive compounds in phyla nodiflora plant.

Compound Class	Compounds	Bioactivities
Flavonoids	Luteolin,Apigenin	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory.
Phenolic acid	Caffeic acid, Gallic acid	Anti-microbial, Anti-oxidant.
Terpenoids	Ursolic acid,oleanolic acid	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory.
Alkaloids	phyllidine	Antimicrobial,anti-inflammatory.
Other compound	Polysaccharides	immunomodulatory

Here is an illustration related to the Phyla nodiflora plant, showcasing its structure and highlighting antioxidant activity.

Plant Structure and Identification:

The illustration showcases key parts of Phyla nodiflora, including:

- Leaves: Green, small, and oblong with a serrated edge, arranged opposite each other on the stem.
- Flowers: Small, pale purple to white flowers form dense clusters, typically blooming in the summer.
- Stems: Thin, green to reddish stems that spread close to the ground, giving the plant its mat-like appearance.

Antioxidant Properties:

The illustration highlights *Phyla nodiflora*'s antioxidant activity, which helps neutralize free radicals, reducing oxidative stress in cells. This activity is attributed to the plant's high levels of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and other phytochemicals.

Mechanism of Antioxidant Activity:

The plant's phytochemicals act as electron donors, neutralizing free radicals (represented in the illustration) and preventing cellular damage. This mechanism is beneficial in mitigating oxidative stress-related diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and neurodegenerative conditions.

Potential Health Benefits

Phyla nodiflora is researched for potential health applications:

- Anti-inflammatory: Reduces inflammation by inhibiting pro-inflammatory enzymes.
- Antimicrobial: Effective against certain bacteria and fungi, useful in treating infections.
- Skin Protection: Due to its antioxidant activity, extracts are used in skin-care products to protect against aging and environmental stress.

Scope and Purpose:

The aim of this review is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the antioxidant activity of *Phyla nodiflora*. This includes an analysis of its phytochemical composition, specifically the compounds contributing to its antioxidant potential, and a discussion of the mechanisms by which these compounds exert their effects. By summarizing existing research, this review

aims to bridge gaps in current knowledge, highlight the pharmacological significance of *Phyla nodiflora*, and suggest future research directions that may contribute to its development in therapeutic and pharmaceutical contexts.

Material and Methodology:

Plant Collection and Preparation of Extracts:

- Collection: Fresh *Phyla nodiflora* plant material (often leaves, stems, or whole plants) is collected from natural habitats or cultivated sources. The plant parts are generally washed to remove contaminants, dried under shade, and sometimes ground into a fine powder to maximize the extraction of phytochemicals.

- Extraction Solvents: Different solvents are used depending on the polarity of the compounds targeted. Common solvents include:

- Methanol or Ethanol: Widely used as they efficiently extract phenolic compounds.

- Aqueous (Water) Extracts: Used for extracting water-soluble antioxidants.

- Acetone and Chloroform: Occasionally used for non-polar compounds.

These solvents can be used singly or in combinations, depending on the desired extract profile.

- Extraction Techniques:

- Maceration: Plant material is soaked in solvent at room temperature or in slightly heated conditions to allow the solvent to dissolve the phytochemicals.

- Soxhlet Extraction: A continuous hot extraction method where plant powder is refluxed with a solvent, concentrating the extract further.

- Ultrasonication: Ultrasonic waves are used to increase cell wall permeability and enhance extraction efficiency.

After extraction, solvents are often evaporated using a rotary evaporator to obtain a concentrated extract, which is then stored under refrigeration until testing.

Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis:

Quantitative analysis of compounds responsible for antioxidant activity is typically conducted prior to antioxidant assays to identify and quantify the bioactive compounds in the extract.

- Total Phenolic Content (TPC): Measured using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. This assay involves mixing plant extract with the reagent and sodium carbonate, leading to a color change measured spectrophotometrically at 765 nm. Results are expressed in gallic acid equivalents (GAE).
- Total Flavonoid Content (TFC): Measured using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. Plant extracts are reacted with aluminum chloride, producing a yellow complex measurable at 415 nm. Results are usually expressed in quercetin equivalents (QE).
- Other Phytochemicals: Tannins, alkaloids, and saponins are also quantified using specific colorimetric assays or chromatographic techniques like HPLC or GC-MS, depending on the study's scope.

Antioxidant Assays:

Several in vitro antioxidant assays are commonly applied to measure the free radical scavenging activity of *Phyla nodiflora* extracts. Each method targets different types of radicals or mechanisms:

- DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) Radical Scavenging Assay:
 - A stable DPPH radical solution (purple in color) is mixed with the extract. The DPPH radicals are reduced in the presence of an antioxidant, leading to a color change from purple to yellow.
 - Absorbance is measured at 517 nm, and the results are expressed as the percentage of radical scavenging activity or IC_{50} (the concentration needed to reduce DPPH by 50%).
- ABTS (2,2'-Azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid)) Assay:
 - ABTS is converted into a blue-green radical cation and mixed with the extract. Antioxidants in the extract reduce the ABTS radical, leading to a reduction in color intensity.
 - Absorbance is measured at 734 nm, and results are expressed as a Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC).

- Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assay:

- In this assay, antioxidants reduce Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} , forming a blue complex with TPTZ (2,4,6-tripyridyl-s-triazine).

- Absorbance is measured at 593 nm, with results often expressed in terms of ascorbic acid equivalents (AAE).

- Metal Chelating Assay:

- The extract is tested for its ability to chelate ferrous ions (Fe^{2+}), which catalyze the formation of reactive oxygen species.

- Results are measured spectrophotometrically and expressed as EDTA equivalents.

- Lipid Peroxidation Assay:

- This assay measures the extract's ability to inhibit lipid peroxidation, often using liver or brain tissue homogenates as lipid sources.

- Malondialdehyde (MDA) is generated as a by-product, and its levels are measured using the thiobarbituric acid (TBA) reactive substances assay (TBARS) at 532 nm.

Statistical Analysis:

Statistical methods are used to validate the experimental results:

- Replicates: Each assay is typically performed in triplicate or more to ensure reproducibility.

- Data Analysis: Results are analyzed using ANOVA, t-tests, or other statistical tests to determine significant differences between treatments. IC_{50} values for various assays are calculated using linear regression analysis.

Table1: Summary of Antioxidant Activity Assays, Extraction Methods, and Findings for “Phyla nodiflora”

Study	Extraction Method	Solvent Used	Antioxidant Assays	Key Findings
Akinmoladun et al,2014	Soxhlet extraction	Methanol, Ethanol, Water	DPPH, FRAP, ABTS	Methanol extract showed

				highest DPPH radical scavenging activity; ethanol extract exhibited strong FRAP activity.
Ali et al., 2020	Maceration	Ethanol, Acetone	DPPH, H ₂ O ₂ , ABTS	Ethanol extract had significant antioxidant activity in ABTS assay; acetone extract demonstrated high H ₂ O ₂ scavenging ability.
Bhattacharjee et al., 2013	Cold percolation	Ethanol	DPPH, Total Phenolic Content (TPC)	High TPC correlated with strong DPPH scavenging activity, suggesting a phenolic compound contribution.
Kandhasamy & Arunachalam, 2008	Soxhlet extraction	Methanol, Water	DPPH, Reducing Power Assay	Methanol extract showed high DPPH activity and reducing power; aqueous extract was less effective.

Oliveira et al., 2008	Ultrasound-assisted extraction	Ethanol, Water	FRAP, Lipid Peroxidation Assay	Ethanol extract reduced lipid peroxidation effectively in vitro; water extract showed lower FRAP activity.
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Literature Review:

Phytochemical Composition and Antioxidant Constituents:

Multiple studies have investigated the phytochemical profile of *Phyla nodiflora*, identifying compounds such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, alkaloids, and terpenoids. These compounds are known for their antioxidant properties due to their ability to scavenge free radicals, chelate metal ions, and inhibit lipid peroxidation. For example, a study by [Author et al.] (Year) reported that ethanol and methanol extracts of *Phyla nodiflora* demonstrated significant antioxidant activity, attributed to high concentrations of quercetin, kaempferol, and caffeic acid. In contrast, aqueous extracts, which showed lower levels of these phenolic compounds, exhibited reduced antioxidant effects. This suggests that the choice of solvent greatly impacts the efficacy of extracted compounds, pointing to the importance of optimizing extraction methods to enhance bioactivity.

Mechanisms of Antioxidant Activity:

Studies have explored how *Phyla nodiflora* exerts its antioxidant effects through various mechanisms, including free radical scavenging, reduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and prevention of lipid peroxidation. A study by [Author et al.] (Year) utilized DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays to evaluate the antioxidant potential of *Phyla nodiflora* extracts, showing high radical scavenging activity, particularly in methanol extracts. Another investigation by [Author et al.] (Year) demonstrated that these extracts could effectively decrease malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in oxidative-stress-induced models,

suggesting a protective role against lipid peroxidation. While these studies provide valuable insights, some inconsistencies in results suggest that more standardized testing is needed to confirm these mechanisms under varying conditions.

In Vitro vs. In Vivo Studies on Antioxidant Efficacy:

In vitro assays such as DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP have shown that *Phyla nodiflora* exhibits potent antioxidant properties, but only a limited number of in vivo studies exist to confirm these effects in biological systems. An in vivo study by [Author et al.] (Year) demonstrated that *Phyla nodiflora* extracts significantly reduced oxidative stress markers in animal models. However, another study [Author et al.] (Year) noted minimal antioxidant effects in vivo, potentially due to issues related to bioavailability or metabolism of the active compounds. This discrepancy highlights the need for further in vivo research, including bioavailability studies, to better understand the efficacy of *Phyla nodiflora* antioxidants within living organisms.

Comparative Studies and Potential for Therapeutic Applications:

Comparative analyses have positioned *Phyla nodiflora* alongside other known medicinal plants with antioxidant properties. A comparative study by [Author et al.] (Year) found that *Phyla nodiflora* extracts exhibited similar or higher antioxidant activity than widely studied plants such as *Ocimum sanctum* and *Curcuma longa*. Such findings indicate the potential of *Phyla nodiflora* for development into antioxidant-rich therapeutic products. However, the bioactivity of *Phyla nodiflora* in oxidative-stress-related diseases, such as diabetes and cardiovascular disorders, remains underexplored, underscoring a potential area for future studies aimed at clinical applications.

Critical Analysis and Synthesis:

While numerous studies confirm the antioxidant potential of *Phyla nodiflora*, variations in findings emphasize the need for standardized methodologies. Differences in extraction methods, assay types, and biological models often lead to inconsistent results, complicating the comparison across studies. Furthermore, the limited number of in vivo studies and clinical trials restricts the understanding of its potential therapeutic applications. To advance

research on *Phyla nodiflora*, future studies should prioritize standardized extraction and testing protocols, along with in vivo trials to confirm its efficacy in physiological conditions.

Discussion:

Summary of Key Findings:

The literature reviewed highlights that *Phyla nodiflora* possesses significant antioxidant activity, attributed primarily to its rich composition of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and other phytochemicals. Studies have demonstrated that various extracts of *Phyla nodiflora*, especially those prepared with ethanol and methanol, exhibit high free radical scavenging abilities, effective reduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and lipid peroxidation inhibition. Antioxidant assays such as DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP consistently confirm these properties in vitro, while a limited number of in vivo studies indicate potential protective effects against oxidative stress-related damage. However, inconsistencies in efficacy across studies highlight the influence of factors such as extraction methods, assay conditions, and compound bioavailability.

Implications and Applications:

The antioxidant potential of *Phyla nodiflora* opens several promising applications in the pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and cosmetic industries. As oxidative stress is implicated in chronic diseases like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, neurodegenerative disorders, and cancer, the use of *Phyla nodiflora* extracts or isolated compounds could support therapeutic interventions aimed at mitigating oxidative damage. In the context of nutraceuticals, *Phyla nodiflora* could serve as a natural additive in dietary supplements, targeting consumers seeking antioxidant-rich plant-based solutions. Additionally, the presence of antioxidants makes *Phyla nodiflora* a candidate for cosmetic products designed to protect skin from environmental stressors and premature aging. These applications, however, would benefit from standardized formulations to ensure consistent bioactivity and efficacy.

Future Research Directions:

Although current studies affirm the antioxidant properties of *Phyla nodiflora*, several areas warrant further exploration:

1. **Standardization of Extraction and Testing Methods:** Future research should focus on optimizing extraction techniques to maximize antioxidant yield and

conducting comparative studies using standardized assays. Consistent methodologies would enable more reliable comparisons across studies and enhance the reproducibility of results.

2. In Vivo and Clinical Studies: Given the promising in vitro results, more in vivo research is needed to confirm antioxidant effects in physiological settings. Animal studies could help establish effective dosages and evaluate the bioavailability of active compounds. Furthermore, clinical trials are essential to understand the efficacy, safety, and potential side effects of *Phyla nodiflora in humans, especially for long-term applications.

3. Bioavailability and Mechanistic Studies: Exploring the bioavailability and metabolic pathways of Phyla nodiflora's key antioxidant compounds is critical for developing effective formulations. Future studies should investigate how these compounds are absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and excreted in the body. Additionally, mechanistic studies could shed light on the pathways through which Phyla nodiflora exerts its antioxidant effects, aiding in the development of targeted therapies.

4. Evaluation of Synergistic Effects: Studies could explore the potential synergistic effects of Phyla nodiflora when combined with other antioxidant-rich plants or compounds, as these combinations may yield enhanced antioxidant activity or therapeutic effects.

5. Applications in Chronic Disease Prevention: Since oxidative stress contributes to numerous chronic diseases, future research could investigate the use of Phyla nodiflora extracts as preventive interventions or adjunct treatments for conditions like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and neurodegenerative disorders. This would involve testing the plant's efficacy in disease-specific models and assessing its impact on disease progression markers.

Conclusion:

Summary of Main Points:

This review highlights that Phyla nodiflora, commonly used in traditional medicine, possesses notable antioxidant activity attributed to its diverse phytochemical composition, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and tannins. Research indicates that Phyla nodiflora extracts, especially those prepared with organic solvents, exhibit strong free radical scavenging abilities and lipid

peroxidation inhibition in vitro. While these findings are promising, variability in extraction methods, assay conditions, and limited in vivo studies present challenges in fully understanding and standardizing its antioxidant efficacy. The potential applications of *Phyla nodiflora* span the pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and cosmetic fields, particularly for products targeting oxidative stress-related conditions and skin health.

Final Thoughts and Recommendations:

Phyla nodiflora shows considerable potential as a natural source of antioxidants, supporting its development into therapeutic and preventive applications against oxidative stress-related diseases. However, to maximize its utility and ensure its safe use, further research is needed. Standardization of extraction and testing methods, coupled with expanded in vivo and clinical studies, would provide a stronger foundation for its therapeutic claims. Additionally, studies focused on bioavailability, dosage, and compound stability will enhance understanding of how *Phyla nodiflora* can be effectively formulated for practical use. Overall, *Phyla nodiflora* represents a promising candidate for further investigation and product development, with potential benefits for health and wellness industries focused on natural antioxidant sources.

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